

THE ROLE OF CULTURAL AND SOCIAL ASPECTS OF ENGLISH SLANGS USED BY YOUTH IN TRANSLATION PROCESS INTO UZBEK

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Abstract This article is devoted to explore linguistic, cultural and social peculiarities of slang words; investigates translation methods and techniques of English slangs used by youth into Uzbek; and analyzes differences between slangs and other standard lexical units of a language. Some basic requirements of translation process of slang expressions were mentioned insightfully.

Key words: slang, translation principles, linguistic features of slang words, social features of slang words, cultural features of slang words.

Introduction

The art of translation is a challenging process and requires a special skill to translate successfully. Translators must be not only linguistically knowledgeable, but also he/she must be familiar with the social, cultural and historical background of a particular language. When it is concerned about the translation process of slangs, translator has to be a person with a wide range of general knowledge, rich life experience, and an advanced culture. The translator must know the life and living conditions of the people he/she is translating from.

Slang is a kind of linguistic device that widely used by people from all walks of life. Any slangs are formed and developed with the history of the language. It has its unique characteristics and functions. For instance, English slangs figure out and describe English culture. A sociolinguistic study of slangs helps us to investigate more detailed data about the culture and society of the language. We are going to

discuss the translation of slangs from English into Uzbek, focusing on cultural, social and historical perspectives.

When we study a slang in terms of its cultural and social values there are some exact differences rather than standard vocabulary of a language.

1. Humor. Mostly, English slangs are considered as "comedy" because of its humorous effect. The humor of English slang first represented in terms of its phonetic aspects. A great amount of English slangs takes advantage of the euphony to achieve the aim of being easily to be understood and remembered and to get the purposes of being readable and vivid. Rhyme is a common phonetic method in American slang to get its humorous effect. There are many examples:

the bee's knees (outstanding people or thing) – mashhur shaxs yoki narsa

fender-bender (a trifle) – arzimagan narsa, ikir-chikir

razzle-dazzle (carnival) – karnaval

2. Conciseness. Conciseness may not be the soul of English slang, but it is perhaps the chief feature. This is attained either by apocope, as in vamp for vampire, molt for muttonhead, fan for fanatic (apparently), etc., or by the substitution of an expressive monosyllable or compound of monosyllables for a longer word or description.

Simp (stupid person) – axmoq odam

Veep (vice president) – Vitse prezident

classy (fashionable) – po'rim, olifta.

They are brief and easy to speak out. When they defined a Communist as either a crank or a crook, the subject is really exhausted. It is difficult now to imagine how we got on so long without the word stunt, how they expressed the characteristics so conveniently summed up in dope-fiend or high-brow, or any other possible way of describing that mixture of the cheap pathetic and the ludicrous which is now universally labeled sob stuff.

3. Originality. Slang is the diction that results from the favorite game among the young and lively of playing with words and renaming things and actions; some invent new words, or mutilate or misapply the old, for the pleasure of novelty, and others catch up such words for the pleasure of being in the fashion. For example, live wire, smoker eater and flying coffin refer to "living man", "fireman", "plane" respectively. These similes are so novel and vivid that they can't be made without good imagination, while

think-machine (brain) - ong

sparkler (diamond) - olmos

pickers (hands) – qo 'llar

are more vivid and expressive. Sometimes slang words are invented by a few people for the pleasure of novelty and imitated by others who like to be in fashion. Many of the slang words coined during the Second World War have passed out of use along with the events that called them into life.

4. Instability. Whereas the words which form the backbone of the language still show no signs of failing variety, it is unusual for slang words to remain in use for more than a few years, though some slang terms serve a useful purpose and so pass into the standard language. The vocabulary of slang changes rapidly: what is new and exciting for one generation is old-fashioned for the next. Old slang often either drifts into obsolescence or becomes accepted into the standard language, losing its eccentric color. *Flapper*, for instance, started life in the late 19th century as a slang term for a young unconventional or lively woman, but subsequently moved into the general language as a specific term for such a vogue woman of the 1920s. Similarly, the use of *gay* in the sense "homosexual" has its roots firmly in slang of the 1930s, but is now widely accepted as standard terminology.

Conclusion

To conclude, it can be mentioned that slangs are a type of linguistic units which convey not only lexical meaning, but also cultural, social and historical

markers in them. In translation process of English slangs into Uzbek there can be applied different methods and techniques, such as using equivalence, direct translation, giving description and etc. this process requires special linguistic, cultural, social and historical knowledge and life experience from the translator.

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